

NEW PERSPECTIVES AND TRENDS ON HISTORY OF TURKESTAN AUTONOMY IN THE WORKS OF LOCAL AND FOREIGN SCHOLARS

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Annotation . The article discusses the historiography of Turkestan Autonomy, which has an important place in the history of Uzbek statehood. Also, the opinions expressed unilaterally by Soviet scientists about autonomy were analyzed, and the scientific research works of foreign and local scientists were evaluated in this regard.

Key words . Autonomy, Jadids, "Sho'rai Islamiya", legitimacy, congress, idea, Bolsheviks.

Turkestan Autonomy, which left a deep mark in the historical memory of our people, is the first national-democratic state that has a special place in the history of Uzbek statehood. Today, this experience of statehood is being evaluated as a path worthy of the national recovery processes being implemented in our country, the chosen path of our people.

It is known that Jadids, the ideologues of the autonomist movement, defined the main directions of building a secular-democratic state in Turkestan. This process included the need to reform all spheres of education, economy, culture and society in general.

In that historical period, the Jadids could foresee how difficult it would be to separate from Russia and develop independently, and Turkestan would fall into a difficult situation. Because Turkestan was economically connected with the Russian Empire in every way . For this reason, they put independent development in the single economic framework on the agenda, and in this regard, they were in favor of giving Turkistan national-territorial autonomy with wide powers.

In this regard, "Shurai Islamiya" (March 1917), "Shurai Ulamo" (June 1917), "Turan" Societies and "Turkish People Centralization Party (Federalists)" (July 1917), "Ittifaqi Muslimin" (September 1917) The formation of political parties was one of the important steps towards the establishment of autonomy.

Unfortunately, the activities of this legitimate state were regularly criticized by the Soviet government, and the activities of the autocrats were negatively evaluated for many years. For example, in two documents dated November 27, 1917 and December 1, 1917, the Turkestan Autonomy is stated as a "bourgeois-nationalist" government, and the authors of the collection (I.T. Bezrukova, M.L. Weiss, M.I. Vekselman, N.V. .Mandalskaya, K.Z. Mukhsinovalar) unjustifiably violated the appeals of the legal Turkestan Autonomy dated November 27, 2017, December 1, 1917, tried to artificially assimilate the meaning of this document into the Soviet policy and ideology, and completely falsified the historical truth. However, Mustafa Chokayev, the Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Turkestan Autonomous Region, who later became the Prime Minister, quoted the above two documents as they actually are, i.e. "Turkestansky vestnik", Tashkent, December 5, 1917, No. 18, "Ot vremennogo pravitelstva avtonomnogo Turkestana"[1].

On the threshold of Uzbekistan's independence, M. Hasanov, one of the local scientists, was the first to give a positive assessment of the legitimacy of Turkestan Autonomy and criticized the above situations [2]. In his article, he criticizes the fact that the Fourth Congress of Muslims of the country on November 26, 1917 was called a "nationalist gathering" for many years: "... How many decades have passed, and even the 20th century is coming to an end, that many of my fellow historians have come to this congress" they stick the label "Nationalists' Gathering". How is it actually? In my opinion, to say so in the full sense is nothing but dishonesty, hypocrisy, hypocrisy. After all, a number of representatives of national intellectuals with a democratic mood expressed such opinions in the session that a narrow-minded nationalist would not have been able to express them."

Professor R.Shamsutdinov emphasized the bloodbath of the Turkestan Autonomy by the Bolsheviks in his several scientific studies [3]. For example, the author emphasizes that the chairman of the Tashkent Soviet, I. O. Tobolin, did not hide his opinion against the establishment of Turkestan autonomy, and cites his following opinions: "...However, there can be no talk of immediate implementation of autonomy. After all, according to the first condition of autonomy, military troops must be withdrawn from this country. If we were to implement this basic condition arising from the concept of autonomy, then we would have struck the edge of the revolution, and the counter-revolutionaries would have reigned in the country. " In other words, the Congress states that it refused to recognize the Turkestan Autonomous Government, declared its members outlawed, and even decided to imprison their leaders.

R.Shamsutdinov in his other research focused on the main aspects of the establishment of Turkestan Autonomy, as well as the role of the government in the socio-political processes of that time [4].

In another scientific research of the author, the opinion was given about Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Obidjon Mahmudov and others who played the main role in the establishment of Turkestan Autonomy [5].

In a number of scientific studies of the author, valuable information about the life and activities of the members of Turkestan Autonomy is given.

Another scientist, S. Agzamkhodjaev, in his work, reflected on the ideological foundations of the establishment of the Turkestan Autonomy, its practical significance, and gave information about the programs and management of the autonomists [6]. The author also gave interesting information about the congresses of Muslims of Turkestan, which were important for the establishment of autonomy. In his research , S.Agzamkhodjaev provided important information about the role, goals and tasks of the "Shuroi Islamiya" organization in the organization of autonomy [7].

Foreign scholars, like Timur Kochoaglu (son of Timur Khoja) regretfully mentions in his book that the conflicts and problems between the "Shorayi Islamiya" and "Shorayi Ulamo" organizations of the Jadids led to the termination of Turkestan Autonomy [8].

In his book, Khalid Adib reflected on the emergence and development of the Jadidist movement in Central Asia and the establishment of Turkestan Autonomy. In this work, the author thought extensively about the specific aspects of autonomy and its leaders. Especially, in the 9th chapter of the book, the work of the Minister of Food of the Turkestan Autonomous Region, Obidjon Mahmudov, was specially touched upon [9].

Also, Khalid Adib's work "The Soviet Assault on Islam", which discusses the role of Islam in society in the years before and after the rule of the Soviets in Central Asia, the importance of religious and secular education in the development of the Jadid movement. The change of religious education in the old style as a result of the modern reform is described in the 9th chapter. In his book, Edward Alworth describes the 130-year rule of Czarist Russia and the Soviet Union in Central Asia, and mentions information about Jadidism, the movement of young Bukharas and young Khivas. The author writes that the above actions motivated the establishment of Turkestan Autonomy [10].

From the above, it can be concluded that although the research conducted in our country and the world on the history of the Turkestan Autonomy, the first national-democratic state, has made it possible to determine many issues about this government, there are still many tasks ahead and problems that need to be studied. Deeper and fair study of the history of the Turkestan Autonomy and its ministers, evaluating them, is of urgent importance in creating the true history of Uzbekistan at that time, in conveying it to the people, and most importantly in educating young people on the basis of patriotic ideas.

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